

Supporting Information for Rewiring Receptor Activation: Mechanistic Insights into Toggle Switch Modulation by 25CN-NBx Compounds

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Computational Details

Initial Structures

The holo-structure of the 5-HT_{2A}R bound to the selective agonist (**1**) was obtained from the RCSB-PDB (PDB ID: 6WHA).¹ Missing extracellular loops were filled using chain B of the holo-structure of the 5-HT_{2A}R bound to LSD (PDB ID: 6WGT), and missing heavy atoms and hydrogens were added using the tleap module of the AMBER22 package.² For (**1**) and all substituted compounds under investigation, the predominant titration state in an aqueous solution at neutral pH is the protonated form ($\text{pK}_a > 7.8$); thus, this state was selected for all simulations.³ The geometries were optimized at the B3LYP/cc-pVDZ level of theory^{4,5} and used to calculate the restricted electrostatic potential charges at the Hartree-

Fock/6-31G* level of theory, ensuring consistency within the AMBER force field.⁶ All the ligands were manually inserted into the orthosteric binding pocket, aligning their structures with that of the crystallized (**1**). All membrane-protein-ligand systems were constructed using CHARMM-GUI.⁷ The protein was oriented along the z-axis using the orientations of proteins in membranes database and the positioning of proteins in membrane web server.⁸ Subsequently, N- and C- termini were amidated and acetylated. The resulting structure was then embedded within a 1-palmitoyl-2-oleoyl-*sn*-glycero-3-phosphocholine lipid bilayer with dimensions of 50 x 50 lipid components in the xy plane and solvated in a rectangular box with aqueous solvent and NaCl at a concentration of 0.15 mol/L. Potential parameters for the protein, lipids, water, and ligands were taken from FF19SB, Lipid21, TIP3P, and GAFF2, respectively.⁹⁻¹²

Classical Molecular Dynamics Simulations

Classical molecular dynamics (MD) simulations for the solvated membrane-protein-ligand systems were performed using the CUDA version of the AMBER20 package.^{2,13} First, energy minimization was carried out with the steepest descent method for 5000 steps, followed by the conjugate gradient method for additional 5000 steps. Positional restraints were applied to the membrane-protein-ligand system, gradually decreasing from 10 to 0.5 kcal/(mol Å²), while heating from 0 to 303.15 K using the Langevin thermostat for a total of 750 ps. The desired density was reached by running an equilibration in the NPT ensemble with a Monte Carlo barostat and semi-isotropic pressure scaling for 500 ps. An unconstrained production run was carried out at 303.15 K for 100 ns, followed by 4 independent copies of 1 μ s (4 μ s per ligand) for a total simulation time of 28 μ s. During the full MD protocol, a timestep of 2 fs was employed. The cutoff radius and switching distance for computing the non-bonded interactions were set to 10.0 Å and 9.0 Å, respectively, and bond lengths involving hydrogen atoms were kept fixed using the SHAKE algorithm.¹⁴ Electrostatic interactions were calculated using the particle-mesh Ewald method with a grid spacing of 1 Å.¹⁵

Umbrella Sampling Simulations

In some replicas of the unbiased MD simulations, W336 was observed to naturally transition from its initial crystallized state with a $\chi_2(\text{W336})$ dihedral angle of $\approx 70^\circ$ to $\approx -20^\circ$. Using the same setup previously described, a representative geometry from the MD simulation was used to start a pulling run, scanning the $\chi_2(\text{W336})$ dihedral angle (reaction coordinate) from 120° to -40° employing a pulling rate of $1^\circ/\text{ns}$ for a total of 160 ns for each compound (1)-(7). The acquired initial geometries were employed to run umbrella sampling (US) simulations with a total of 33 windows evenly spaced 5 degrees apart, to ensure adequate overlap between neighboring distributions. A harmonic restraint with a force constant of 90.0 kcal/mol/rad² was applied to maintain the value of the reaction coordinate, and for some high energy window, a stronger bias potential with a force constant of 150.0 kcal/mol/rad² was employed. For each compound and in each window, a MD trajectory was run for 50 ns, resulting in a total simulation time of 11.55 μs . The weighted histogram analysis method (WHAM) was then employed to calculate the potential of mean force (PMF) along the reaction coordinate using data obtained from each US simulation.^{16,17}

MMGBSA Free Energy Analysis

The relative binding free energy, ΔG_{tot} , decomposed into electrostatic (ΔG_{el}), van der Waals (ΔG_{vdw}), polar solvation (ΔG_{pol}), and non-polar solvation (ΔG_{np}), was calculated for all the ligand-receptor complexes using the 1A-molecular mechanics generalize Born surface area end-state method.¹⁸ A total of 200 equidistant geometries were obtained from the US window corresponding to the global minimum energy for each complex, and a pairwise residue decomposition analysis was performed to further decompose each of the terms into residue-ligand free energies. This allowed for the quantification and characterization of the interactions upon N-benzyl substitution. The same procedure was carried out by treating W336 as the ligand within the ligand-receptor complex, considering the rest of the protein and the 25CN-NBx molecules as the receptor, to characterize the interactions of W336 at

the two minima for the bulky compounds (5)-(7).

References

- (1) Kim, K.; Che, T.; Panova, O.; DiBerto, J. F.; Lyu, J.; Krumm, B. E.; Wacker, D.; Robertson, M. J.; Seven, A. B.; Nichols, D. E. Structure of a hallucinogen-activated Gq-coupled 5-HT_{2A} serotonin receptor. *Cell* **2020**, *182*, 1574–1588. e19.
- (2) Case, D. A.; Aktulga, H. M.; Belfon, K.; Ben-Shalom, I.; Brozell, S. R.; Cerutti, D. S.; Cheatham III, T. E.; Cruzeiro, V. W. D.; Darden, T. A.; Duke, R. E. *Amber 2021*; University of California, San Francisco, 2021.
- (3) Wishart, D. S.; Feunang, Y. D.; Guo, A. C.; Lo, E. J.; Marcu, A.; Grant, J. R.; Sajed, T.; Johnson, D.; Li, C.; Sayeeda, Z.; others DrugBank 5.0: a major update to the DrugBank database for 2018. *Nucleic Acids Res.* **2018**, *46*, D1074–D1082.
- (4) Becke, A. D. Density-functional thermochemistry. III. The role of exact exchange. *J. Chem. Phys.* **1993**, *98*, 5648–5652.
- (5) Dunning Jr, T. H. Gaussian basis sets for use in correlated molecular calculations. I. The atoms boron through neon and hydrogen. *J. Chem. Phys.* **1989**, *90*, 1007–1023.
- (6) Bayly, C. I.; Cieplak, P.; Cornell, W.; Kollman, P. A. A well-behaved electrostatic potential based method using charge restraints for deriving atomic charges: the RESP model. *J. Phys. Chem.* **1993**, *97*, 10269–10280.
- (7) Jo, S.; Kim, T.; Iyer, V. G.; Im, W. CHARMM-GUI: a web-based graphical user interface for CHARMM. *J. Comput. Chem.* **2008**, *29*, 1859–1865.
- (8) Lomize, M. A.; Pogozheva, I. D.; Joo, H.; Mosberg, H. I.; Lomize, A. L. OPM database and PPM web server: resources for positioning of proteins in membranes. *Nucleic Acids Res.* **2012**, *40*, D370–D376.

- (9) Tian, C.; Kasavajhala, K.; Belfon, K. A.; Raguette, L.; Huang, H.; Migués, A. N.; Bickel, J.; Wang, Y.; Pincay, J.; Wu, Q. ff19SB: Amino-acid-specific protein backbone parameters trained against quantum mechanics energy surfaces in solution. *J. Chem Theory Comput.* **2019**, *16*, 528–552.
- (10) Gould, I.; Skjevik, A.; Dickson, C.; Madej, B.; Walker, R. Lipid17: A comprehensive AMBER force field for the simulation of zwitterionic and anionic lipids. *Manuscript in preparation* **2018**,
- (11) Jorgensen, W. L.; Chandrasekhar, J.; Madura, J. D.; Impey, R. W.; Klein, M. L. Comparison of simple potential functions for simulating liquid water. *The Journal of Chemical Physics* **1983**, *79*, 926–935.
- (12) Wang, J.; Wolf, R. M.; Caldwell, J. W.; Kollman, P. A.; Case, D. A. Development and testing of a general amber force field. *J. Comput. Chem.* **2004**, *25*, 1157–1174.
- (13) Salomon-Ferrer, R.; Gotz, A. W.; Poole, D.; Le Grand, S.; Walker, R. C. Routine microsecond molecular dynamics simulations with AMBER on GPUs. 2. Explicit solvent particle mesh Ewald. *J. Chem. Theory. Comput.* **2013**, *9*, 3878–3888.
- (14) Ryckaert, J.-P.; Ciccotti, G.; Berendsen, H. J. Numerical integration of the cartesian equations of motion of a system with constraints: molecular dynamics of n-alkanes. *J. Comput. Phys.* **1977**, *23*, 327–341.
- (15) Darden, T.; York, D.; Pedersen, L. Particle mesh Ewald: An $N \log(N)$ method for Ewald sums in large systems. *J. Chem. Phys.* **1993**, *98*, 10089–10092.
- (16) Kumar, S.; Rosenberg, J. M.; Bouzida, D.; Swendsen, R. H.; Kollman, P. A. The weighted histogram analysis method for free-energy calculations on biomolecules. I. The method. *J. Comput. Chem.* **1992**, *13*, 1011–1021.

- (17) Grossfield, A.; Woolf, T. B. Interaction of tryptophan analogs with POPC lipid bilayers investigated by molecular dynamics calculations. *Langmuir* **2002**, *18*, 198–210.
- (18) Miller III, B. R.; McGee Jr, T. D.; Swails, J. M.; Homeyer, N.; Gohlke, H.; Roitberg, A. E. MMPBSA.py: an efficient program for end-state free energy calculations. *J. Chem. Theory Comput.* **2012**, *8*, 3314–3321.